

Diagnostic tools in veterinary practice

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Diagnosis of a disease is a very crucial aspect for clinicians. It requires a lot of experience, patience & tactful techniques. The role of the clinician to the society is not limited to the treatment of animals but behind this, the important point is to make the exact or successful diagnosis of the disease of animals.

Diagnosis is the art of recognition and determination of the nature of the disease. It is said that a clinician should have the heart of the mother, the energy of a lion & the eyes of an eagle. In veterinary practice, it becomes more difficult due to various limitations and the unavailability of diagnostic equipment at the field level. It is needless to say that animals cannot complain about their grievances or pain so a veterinary clinician can diagnose the disease from the conclusion drawn from various things like history taking, from clinical examination, from laboratory tests & from other diagnostic aids. Some of the diagnostic techniques are summarized here.

From anamnesis

History-taking (anamnesis) plays a significant role in veterinary practice. History taking is the first step to arrive at the diagnosis of a disease. Careful & polite language history should be obtained from the animal owner/attender. Awareness about local language brings the close relationship between client (owner) & clinician. History taking comprises three parts patient data, history of the disease & environmental history.

- a) **Patient data:** The data relating to the patient like age, sex, breed, species play a significant role in the diagnosis of a disease.

age: Some diseases are more common to the young age group, while others are found in the old age group. Eg Rickets found in young ones.

Sex: Some diseases or abnormalities are only found only in females, while some others are found only in males. Eg Milk fever is only found in females.

Breed: Some diseases are breed-specific & found only in these breeds. Eg HF cattle is more prone to metabolic diseases.

Species: Glanders & strangles are found only in equines whereas, enterotoxaemia is found in sheep & goats.

- b) **History of the disease:** In this part, the duration of the disease, signs or symptoms noticed by the attendee or owner of the animal is noted. It includes present/ immediate history & past history.

Present disease history: In this aspect, the present condition of the disease and its symptoms are recorded. i.e. dullness, depression, lameness, appetite, defecation, urination & respiration.

Past history: In this aspect, the description of the past, when the disease occurred should be recorded. The treatment given in the past, their response & morbidity & mortality are also recorded.

- c) **Environmental history/General History:** In this part, the environment of the animal or patient has to be noted. The feeding, watering, nutritional status, climate (humid or dry), etc should be noted. General management practices & breeding status of the animal are also recorded in this history.

Nutrition: Some diseases are caused by changes in nutrition, under diet, or overfeeding. eg. Lactic acidosis occurs due to overfeeding of carbohydrate (cereal) rich diets. Contaminated water may cause a number of diseases like salmonellosis.

Some diseases are found in hot climates; however, others may be found in a cold or humid climate.

Overcrowding, unhygienic condition, poor ventilation, etc may also cause certain diseases.

From the physical examination of the animal

It is the second step in arriving at the conclusion of disease diagnosis. There are three types of examination of the animal or patient.

- Physical methods of examination
- Clinical examination &
- Regional examination

Physical methods of examination include Inspection, palpation, percussion, auscultation & succession.

In clinical examination various body parameters like HBR, RR, PR & temperature are recorded.

In the regional examination, various regions of the body like head, neck, thorax, abdomen, tail, forelimb & hind limb are examined.

Physical methods of examination of the animal

Inspection: Inspection can be made in two ways i.e. observing the patient from the distance or observing the patient by going closer to the patient. While performing an inspection, first of all, we have to observe the animal/ patient from a distance without touching its body parts. The gait of the animal, locomotion, posture, body texture, body conformation, body contour, the color of skin, facial expression, nature of depression, etc should be observed & recorded. It gives clue that which body part is affected. Inspection is very important in lameness cases.

Palpation: This may be second step in the physical examination of the patient or animal. Palpation of the body organs also plays important role in arriving at the conclusion for diagnosis of a disease. In edematous conditions, palpation is helpful in the diagnosis or recognition of the nature of the swelling. i.e. whether it is an abscess, cyst, tumor, hernia, or hematoma. Palpation is very essential in case of pregnancy diagnosis of the patient, either through extra-abdominal or through per-rectal examination. The artery which is supplying blood to the fetus (fremitus) can also be felt by per-rectal palpation.

Percussion: It may be the third step in the physical methods of examination of the patient or animal. In this method, the body organs are forced to vibrate to produce sound. Eg. In case of horn cancer, if we are going to strike percussion hammer to the affected horn, a hollow sound will be produced giving a high pitch. Sometimes percussion also helps in the diagnosis of lameness or abnormality in hooves or claws.

Tactile percussion: It is also termed an allotment. In this method simultaneously, percussion & palpation are to be performed. Per-rectal examination of pregnancy diagnosis mostly we adopt this method. In pre-rectal examination we are going to palpate the uterus & push the underlying organs, the organs of the fetus rebound to our fingers or palm, giving rise to the healthy condition of the fetus. Moreover, if there is hard organs to touch to the hand or leathery feeling is there, then there can be something definitely wrong with the fetus in the womb.

Auscultation: In this method, the sound of the organs is to be heard. The sound may be normal or abnormal. More commonly auscultation can be done for thoracic or abdominal organs. When a stethoscope or phonendoscope (specially designed stethoscope for veterinary practice) is used, then this is known as an indirect method of auscultation.

Succession: Sometimes shaking of the larger part of the body like the abdomen is required by the hands to recognize the nature of the content, this type of shaking of the body by hands is known as succession. However, succession can be practiced only in the case of small animals because of their smaller body sizes.

Clínical examination of the animal

In spite of all these different physical methods of examination of the animal/patient, a clinician must have to take into consideration various other methods like to record pulse rate, heartbeat rate, temperature & respiratory rate. A clinician must be experienced enough to recognize the abnormalities like increased or decreased and nature of different parameters like pulse rate, respiratory rate, temperature & heartbeat. As we know that in most infectious diseases, there will be a rise in the temperature giving conditions like fever. A clinician should be well aware of the normal rate of respiration, pulse rate, heartbeat rate, and temperature in the case of different species of the animals so that abnormalities can be recognized in order to arrive conclusion for the diagnosis. Thorough knowledge of all these physiological parameters is essential for a clinician to make an exact or successful diagnosis of a disease.

The regional examination of the animal

In the second part of the inspection, we have to observe the different body parts starting from the head to the tail of the animal by going nearer to the animal. First of all, the head or face has to be examined for its symmetry on both sides. Eyes should be examined for any lacrimation, mouth for salivation subsequently nose, nostrils, and ear should be examined. After observing the head, the neck should be examined then the thorax, abdomen, anus for defecation, urogenital organs, etc should be observed. And lastly, forelimbs & hind limbs should be examined for any abnormalities or defects.

From the symptoms, we may reach up to the system which is affected in the patient/animal. From the system, we can enlist the differential diagnosis of that particular system in our mental horizon. By this technique, we can draw the conclusion for the tentative diagnosis of a disease.

From laboratory tests

It is said that the laboratory cannot diagnose a case without a clinician. There are a number of laboratory tests to detect various types of abnormalities. Thorough knowledge of all these tests is essential for a clinician. eg. mastitis can be detected by the California mastitis test. Various hematological examinations can reveal blood-related abnormalities in the animals (Thrall *et al.* 2012). Urinalysis performed properly is a highly reliable index of renal disease (Parrah *et al.* 2013).

From other diagnostic aids

There are other diagnostic aids from which we can draw conclusions for the diagnosis of various diseases. Main among these aids are

- Radiography
- Ultrasonography
- CT Scan
- MRI
- Scintigraphy & Gamma cameras

With the help of all these techniques, we can draw a conclusion about the detection or diagnosis of the diseases. The detailed knowledge of all these techniques is essential to draw the conclusion for a successful diagnosis of the disease. All these techniques have some merits or demerits. Eg In CT Scan we can produce a number of images within a fraction of seconds, however, there is a risk of a huge degree of radiation. Repeated exposure to such radiation produces biological effects of radiation.

Hence nutshell we say that successful diagnosis of any disease or deformities can be diagnosed by all these methods. A disease can be diagnosed by applying any one or more techniques depending upon the nature of the disease or the experience of a clinician. Moreover, the clinician has to be interested always in acquiring knowledge of the latest advanced technique in the field. A clinician must update the latest knowledge available. eg. In the case of urolithiasis, when people are going to perform cystotomy in the case of cattle calf or buffalo

calf, fixation of folly's catheter is the advanced research in retention or urine. This is bypass surgery in such types of cases. There are other such advancements that may be available. A clinician must be always must be in touch with these latest advancements.

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